

Eastern England SDE Airlock Manager Model Disclosure Control Standard Operating Procedure

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Purpose and Scope

This guidance supports airlock managers (Output Checkers) when reviewing machine-learning models submitted for egress.

This document should be used in conjunction with the SDC airlock manager SOP, which provides the baseline governance process for output checking. The current document extends that process specifically for machine-learning models using SACRO-ML.

In addition to disclosure risk assessment, this SOP introduces model-specific checks, including:

- Membership inference risk assessment using SACRO-ML
- Validation against the approved AI Risk Assessment
- Review of model design, inputs, and outputs
- Assessment of any agreed actionable controls

The airlock manager must ensure that model outputs are both:

- Safe from a disclosure perspective
- Consistent with the approved project scope and AI Risk Assessment

What the Researcher Must Provide

For a model to be assessed, the researcher must supply at minimum:

1. Model file
 - e.g. model.pkl (sklearn/joblib), or equivalent for the framework in use.
2. Data used for training and testing
 - train_X.npy
 - train_y.npy
 - test_X.npy
 - test_y.npy
 - (or clearly named equivalents)
3. README / model card

Brief description of:

1. Model name and purpose
 - e.g. “Case – Diabetes multifactor Random Forest”
2. Model type
 - e.g. RandomForestClassifier
3. Features used
 - e.g. n_visits, n_conditions, n_drugs, n_measurements, n_procedures
4. Outcome definition
 - e.g. has_diabetes
5. Any important preprocessing steps

If any of these are missing, request for clarification.

Alignment with AI Risk Assessment and Control Verification

Before conducting SACRO-ML checks, the airlock manager must verify that the submitted model aligns with the approved AI Risk Assessment and that any agreed controls have been implemented.

The AI Risk Assessment defines:

- Approved model type
 - e.g. Random Forest, Logistic Regression
- Input features and data sources
- Output variables
- Intended use of the model
- Identified risks and agreed mitigations

Alignment checks:

The airlock manager should confirm that:

- The submitted model matches the approved architecture
- The features used are consistent with those approved
- The outputs and predictions align with the intended analytical purpose
- No additional or unapproved modelling approaches have been introduced

Verification of agreed controls

Where the AI Risk Assessment or prior governance discussions have identified actionable controls (e.g. model simplification, feature restrictions, output constraints), the airlock manager must verify that these have been implemented.

This should be assessed using:

- The README or model card
- Supporting documentation provided by the researcher

Action if issues are identified

If alignment cannot be confirmed, or if expected controls are not present or are insufficiently implemented:

- Request clarification from the researcher
- Do not proceed to approval until the issue is resolved
- Follow the misalignment handling process where appropriate

Handling Model Misalignment with Approved Scope

In addition to disclosure risk, the airlock manager must ensure that the model being submitted is consistent with what was approved in the AI Risk Assessment.

Examples of misalignment include:

- A different model type than originally approved
- Additional or unapproved input features
- Different target variable or prediction task
- Changes in model complexity or structure

- Outputs that do not match the approved analytical objective

Action to be taken:

- Minor issues
 - Request clarification via service desk
- Moderate concerns
 - Request justification and supporting documentation
 - Consider whether updates or mitigation are required
- Major misalignment
 - Do not approve the model for egress
 - Inform the researcher that the submission does not align with the approved AI Risk Assessment
 - Advise that an updated risk assessment or governance approval may be required

The airlock manager is empowered to reject models that do not align with the approved scope, even if SACRO-ML metrics appear acceptable.

Additional Verification and Request for Supporting Evidence

In some cases, SACRO-ML outputs or initial checks may indicate potential overfitting, data leakage, or inconsistencies in model behaviour. Where this occurs, the airlock manager may require additional evidence to support a robust disclosure decision.

When additional verification may be required

This may include situations where:

- SACRO-ML metrics indicate elevated risk
 - e.g. high AUC or Advantage
- Model performance appears unusually high relative to dataset size or complexity
- There is inconsistency between the model description and observed outputs
- The model structure suggests potential memorisation
 - e.g. very deep trees, low regularisation
- There are concerns about how training and testing data have been separated

Actions available to the airlock manager

The airlock manager may request:

- Access to the researcher's model training or evaluation code
- Clarification on data splitting methodology
 - e.g. train/test separation
- Re-running evaluation using a reserved or held-out dataset, where available
- Additional model performance metrics

- e.g. training vs test performance comparison

Where appropriate, the airlock manager may also reproduce parts of the evaluation within the secure environment to verify results.

High-level workflow of SACRO-ML for Output Checkers

When you receive a model egress request:

Set up a checking notebook in the secure environment, create a clean Python notebook in the secure environment.

1. Install or import SACRO-ML, sklearn, numpy

```
import numpy as np
import joblib
from sacroml.attacks.likelihood_attack import LIRAAttack
from sacroml.attacks.target import Target
import os
```

2. Confirm all required files exist

- Model, training and testing data files

3. Load arrays and model

```
X_train = np.load("train_x.npy")
y_train = np.load("train_y.npy")
X_test = np.load("test_x.npy")
y_test = np.load("test_y.npy")
model = joblib.load("model_case.pkl")
```

4. Check shapes and types:

- X_train, X_test have same number of columns
- y_train, y_test are 0/1 or clearly defined labels

5. Wrap model and data into a Target object

```
ATTACK_c2_OUTDIR = "case_lira_outputs"
os.makedirs(ATTACK_c1_OUTDIR, exist_ok=True)
print("\nAttack output directory:", ATTACK_c1_OUTDIR)
target_rf2 = Target(
    model=model,
    dataset_name="case_diabetes_multifeature", -- example
    X_train=X_train,
    y_train=y_train,
    X_test=X_test,
    y_test=y_test,
)
```

6. Run attacks in this order:

- StructuralAttack - optional but recommended if available
- WorstCaseAttack - mandatory

Example:

```
WC_OUTDIR = "case_worstcase_outputs"
```

```

os.makedirs(WC_OUTDIR, exist_ok=True)
print("Worst case output directory:", WC_OUTDIR)
# running the attack
wc_attack = WorstCaseAttack(
    output_dir=WC_OUTDIR,
    write_report=True,
    n_reps=10,
    reproduce_split=5,
    n_dummy_reps=1,
    train_beta=1,
    test_prop=0.2,
    include_model_correct_feature=False,
    sort_probs=True,
)
print("Running the attack on case 2")
wc_report = wc_attack.attack(target_wc)
print("Worst case report saved to:", WC_OUTDIR)

```

7. LIRA Attack - run if WorstCaseAttack does not show severe risk

- Examples

- i. Simple attack without providing any parameters:

```

lira_attack = LIRAAttack(
    n_shadow_models=20,
    output_dir=ATTACK_OUTDIR,
)
print("Running LiRA attack...")
lira_attack.attack(target)
print("LiRA attack done")

```

- ii. Stating more parameters:

```

lira_attack = LIRAAttack(
    output_dir=ATTACK_c2_OUTDIR,
    write_report=True,
    n_shadow_models=20,
    p_thresh=0.05,
    mode="Offline",
    fix_variance=False,
    report_individual=False
)
print("\nRunning Lira attack for case 2...")
lira_attack.attack(target_rf2)
print("Lira attack done. Files saved to:",
      ATTACK_c2_OUTDIR)

```

Interpret the metrics for each attack using the guidance below

```

with open (os.path.join(ATTACK2_OUTDIR, "report.json")) as f:
    print(f.read())

```

Make a decision:

- Approve model for egress.
- Approve with documented caveats.
- Reject and provide feedback to the researcher.

Available SACRO-ML attacks (overview)

Attack	What it does	Typical use
StructuralAttack	Analyses model structure / hyperparameters for degrees of freedom, k-anonymity issues, class disclosure, and small group risk.	Early structural safety check, especially for tree-based models and regressions.
WorstCaseAttack	Runs a “worst case” membership inference attack using model predictive probabilities and re-training on different data splits.	Main screening attack to detect overfitting and structural leakage.
LiRA Attack	Full Likelihood Ratio Attack using shadow models; approximates a realistic attacker with similar data.	Final, strong privacy test for membership inference risk.

Structural Attack

What it checks:

StructuralAttack looks only at the structure and parameters of the model, not clever external attackers. It asks questions like:

- Is the model too complex for the data size?
 - e.g. degrees of freedom
- Could predictions allow class disclosure?
 - e.g. regression with very small groups
- Are there small groups that can be singled out?
- Is there unnecessary risk from hyperparameters?
 - e.g. extremely deep trees

Example:

A decision tree with depth 20 and almost no regularisation trained on 5,000 people – very likely to memorise individuals rather than learn general patterns.

How to use (conceptual steps)

- Load model and data as usual
- Wrap the model in a Target object (if required by the API)
- Create StructuralAttack with a chosen output directory
- Run `attack.attack(target)` or equivalent
- Review JSON/PDF report in the output directory

Refer to the github repo for more information:

https://github.com/AI-SDC/SACRO-ML/blob/main/sacroml/attacks/structural_attack.py

Key metrics and how to read them

Exact field names may vary, but you will see booleans or counts for dof_risk (degrees of freedom risk):

- Meaning:
 - Model has too many parameters relative to data size (likely overfitting)
- Ideal:
 - False
- If True:
 - High structural risk → strongly consider rejecting or asking the researcher to simplify

k_anonymity / small_group_risk

- Meaning:
 - Whether the model is effectively learning from very small groups, e.g. groups of size $< k$
- Ideal:
 - False or k above your policy threshold, e.g. $k \geq 10$
- If risk flagged
 - You may need to ask for grouping, coarsening, or different model design

class_disclosure

- Meaning:
 - Risk that the model directly reveals sensitive target variable structure, e.g. extremely high predicted values for a tiny cluster
- Ideal:
 - False
- If True:
 - Treat as a serious concern and escalate

Use StructuralAttack as “red flag detector” – if triggered, you should not move forward without changes.

WorstCaseAttack

What it checks:

WorstCaseAttack simulates a “bad but not super-smart” attacker who:

- Has access to model probabilities
- Retrains multiple simple attack models on different splits of the data

- Tries to predict which records were in the training set vs not

This identifies if the model is structurally leaking information about membership.

When to use

- Always for ML models being considered for egress
- Use it before running LIRA
- If it already shows high risk, LIRA is unnecessary

How to run (conceptual)

1. Load arrays and model.
2. Wrap the model and data in a Target (or pass probs directly if using `attack_from_preds`).
3. Initialise `WorstCaseAttack`, e.g.:
 - `n_reps` ~ 10 (number of attack repetitions)
 - `p_thresh` ~ 0.05 (significance threshold)
 - `test_prop` ~ 0.2 (proportion for attack test)
4. Run `worst_attack.attack(target)` or `worst_attack.attack_from_preds(...)`
5. Inspect `report.json` / `report.pdf`

Metrics to check (in order of importance)

1. AUC (Area Under ROC Curve)
 - Meaning:
 - How well the attack distinguishes Train vs Test records
 - Ideal range:
 - Around 0.50–0.58
 - Concern:
 - 0.60 → suspicious
 - 0.65 → strong leakage, likely reject
2. Advantage
 - Meaning:
 - How much better the attacker is than random guessing
 - Ideal:
 - < 0.05
 - Concern:
 - 0.05–0.10 → medium risk
 - 0.10 → high risk; seriously consider rejection
3. `n_sig_auc_p_vals` / `n_sig_pdif_p_vals` (or similar)

- Meaning:
 - Number of repetitions where AUC or probability difference is statistically significant ($p < 0.05$)
- Ideal:
 - 0
- Concern:
 - If >0 and AUC/Advantage are high, risk is very likely real

4. Dummy attack metrics

- These measure performance of “dummy” (baseline) attacks
- If dummy attacks perform similarly to the main attack, actual risk may be lower than it looks
- If main attack is clearly stronger than dummy, risk is more serious

5. Decision guidance

- Safe / low risk:
 - $AUC \leq 0.58$
 - Advantage < 0.05
 - Few or no significant p-values
 → Proceed to LIRA for final check.
- Borderline:
 - AUC 0.58–0.60 or Advantage 0.05–0.10
 → Run LIRA; document concerns and watch carefully
- High risk:
 - $AUC \geq 0.65$ or Advantage ≥ 0.10 with significant p-values
 → Strong argument to reject or request model redesign even before LIRA

LIRA Attack (Likelihood Ratio Attack)

What it checks

LIRA is a full membership inference attack using shadow models:

- It simulates an attacker who has similar data and can train their own models
- It computes a likelihood ratio that a record was in the training set
- Outputs detailed metrics for how successful that attack is

This is considered the strongest privacy test currently available using SACRO-ML.

When to use

- For any model that passes StructuralAttack and WorstCaseAttack (or is at least not clearly high risk)
- Required for final sign-off before allowing model egress

How to run (conceptual)

1. Prepare a Target object with:
 - model
 - X_train, y_train
 - X_test, y_test
2. Create output directory: e.g. "case_lira_outputs"
3. Initialise LIRAAttack with parameters such as:
 - output_dir
 - n_shadow_models (e.g. 20)
 - p_thresh (e.g. 0.05)
 - mode="offline" (typical)
4. Run `lira_attack.attack(target)`
5. Read `report.json` and/or `report.pdf`

Metrics to check (in order of importance)

1. AUC
 - Meaning:
 - How good the LIRA attacker is at spotting members
 - Ideal:
 - Under 0.55 → generally safe
 - Concern:
 - 0.55–0.60 → some leakage
 - 0.60 → significant leakage
 - 0.65 → strong leakage; normally reject
2. Advantage
 - Meaning:
 - Improvement over random guessing
 - Ideal:
 - < 0.05
 - Concern:
 - 0.05–0.10 → moderate risk
 - 0.10 → high risk

- 0.15 → very high risk; typically reject
3. PDFI / PDIF / related metrics, these often measure how concentrated the risk is in subgroups
 - Rule of thumb PDFI values:
 - 0–20: low
 - 20–50: moderate
 - 50: serious – indicates small, highly exposed subgroups
 - 100: very serious
 4. TPR / FPR / ACC / F1
 - TPR (True Positive Rate): how often the attacker correctly identifies a member
 - FPR (False Positive Rate): how often they wrongly label non-members as members
 - ACC / F1: overall attack quality
 - If TPR is high while FPR is not too high, this indicates real risk
 5. Significance flags (AUC_sig, PDIF_sig)
 - If “Significant at $p < 0.05$ ” → attack is unlikely to be random noise
 6. Decision guidance
 - Safe / acceptable risk:
 - $AUC < 0.55$
 - Advantage < 0.05
 - PDFI not elevated
 - No strong significance flags

→ Model may be approved (document metrics in the decision)
 - Borderline:
 - $AUC 0.55–0.60$ or Advantage $0.05–0.10$
 - PDFI mildly raised

→ Consider:

 - Are the use-case high benefit and low harm?
 - Are outputs heavily controlled downstream?
 - Might retraining or regularisation reduce risk?

→ Discuss with independent reviewer before approval/rejection.
 - High risk:
 - $AUC \geq 0.60$, Advantage ≥ 0.10 , or PDFI ≥ 50 (especially with “Significant at $p < 0.05$ ”)

→ Strong grounds to reject model or demand re-design (e.g. simpler model, fewer features, more regularisation)

Glossary

Actionable Controls – Specific mitigation measures (e.g. feature restriction, model simplification) agreed during AI Risk Assessment that must be implemented and verified before model egress.

Advantage (Attack Metric) – A metric measuring how much better an attack performs compared to random guessing; higher values indicate stronger membership inference risk.

AI Risk Assessment – A governance document defining approved model design, inputs, outputs, risks, and mitigations, used as the baseline for validating model submissions.

Alignment Check – The process of confirming that the submitted model matches the approved AI Risk Assessment in terms of structure, features, outputs, and purpose.

AUC (Area Under the Curve) – A metric indicating how well an attack distinguishes between training and non-training records; higher values suggest greater disclosure risk.

Attribute Attack – A simulated attack that attempts to infer sensitive attributes from model outputs, assessing additional privacy risks beyond membership inference.

Degrees of Freedom (DoF Risk) – An indicator of whether model complexity is too high relative to dataset size, increasing the likelihood of overfitting and memorisation.

Disclosure Risk – The likelihood that released outputs enable identification of individuals or sensitive attributes, either directly or indirectly.

Dummy Attack – A baseline attack used for comparison to determine whether observed attack performance reflects real risk or random behaviour.

Egress – The process of releasing outputs from a Secure Data Environment, subject to disclosure control checks and approval.

Feature Set (Input Features) – The variables used by the model for training and prediction, which must align with those approved in governance processes.

False Positive Rate (FPR) – The proportion of non-training records incorrectly identified as training records by an attack.

Held-out Dataset – A reserved dataset not used during training, used for additional validation to detect overfitting or leakage.

Hyperparameters – Configuration settings controlling model behaviour (e.g. depth, regularisation), which can influence disclosure risk.

k-anonymity / Small Group Risk – A measure of whether individuals belong to sufficiently large groups; low values increase re-identification risk.

LIRA Attack (Likelihood Ratio Attack) – An advanced membership inference attack using shadow models to estimate realistic disclosure risk.

Memorisation – When a model retains specific training data patterns, increasing the risk of identifying individuals.

Membership Inference Attack – An attack that attempts to determine whether a specific record was used during model training.

Misalignment (Model Misalignment) – A situation where the submitted model differs from the approved design, features, or purpose defined in the AI Risk Assessment.

Model Artefact – The trained model file submitted for release, treated as an output requiring disclosure control assessment.

Model Card / README – Documentation describing the model's purpose, inputs, outputs, and assumptions to support review and transparency.

Model Complexity – The structural sophistication of a model, where higher complexity increases the risk of overfitting and leakage.

Overfitting – When a model performs well on training data but poorly on unseen data, increasing disclosure risk.

PDIF / PDFI (Probability Difference Metrics) – Metrics indicating how concentrated disclosure risk is across individuals or subgroups, with higher values indicating greater risk.

p-value (Significance Testing) – A statistical measure indicating whether observed results are likely due to chance, supporting interpretation of attack results.

Preprocessing – Data transformation steps applied before model training (e.g. scaling, encoding), which must be documented and consistent.

Regularisation – Techniques used to reduce overfitting by constraining model complexity, helping to lower disclosure risk.

Significance Flags (AUC_sig, PDIF_sig) – Indicators showing whether attack results are statistically significant and not due to random variation.

Structural Attack – An analysis of model structure and parameters to identify inherent disclosure risks such as over-complexity or small groups.

Structural Leakage – Disclosure risk arising from the model's internal design, enabling memorisation of specific data points.

Test Data – Data not used during training, used to evaluate model performance and support attack simulations.

Train/Test Split – The division of data into training and testing sets to enable valid evaluation and disclosure risk assessment.

Training Data – The dataset used to train the model, representing the primary source of potential disclosure risk.

True Positive Rate (TPR) – The proportion of training records correctly identified by an attack as members.

WorstCaseAttack – A simulated attack estimating the maximum possible membership inference risk, used as the primary screening test.